

Quantitative Decision Making in Drug Development: Dual Criteria with Multiple Endpoints

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Abstract

The pharmaceutical industry has experienced escalating costs and high late phase attrition rates over the past two decades. Among proposals that address this challenge is the use of quantitative decision-making framework that takes into account currently available information about safety and efficacy of the drug, target product profile, commercial and regulatory needs. In this paper we focus on dual criteria for Go/Pause/NoGo decision making in early phase clinical trials (see Lalonde et al. (2007), Chuang-Stein and Kirby (2017)) as applied to the design of studies with multiple endpoints/biomarkers. Examples of case studies and corresponding operating characteristics are provided.

Key Words: Dual criteria, multiple endpoints, Target value (TV), Lower reference value (LRV)

1. Introduction

Rising costs and high late phase attrition rates present a considerable challenge in drug development. While recent data from the CMR International consortium indicate that success rates from phase III through to launch have slightly increased, from just under 50% at the beginning of the previous decade to about 65% in the 2015-2017 period, the overall probability of success from entry to phase I to launch stays below 10%; see Figure 1 in BIO (2016) and Dowden and Munro (2019). Among reasons for trial failure are a lack of efficacy, issues with safety and problems with patient recruitment and retention. Still, an inability to demonstrate efficacy remains the primary source of trial failure; see Fogel (2018).

The low success rate and the high cost of drug development have motivated pharmaceutical companies to search for better methods to make decisions about progressing a new compound to the next stage of development (Go) or terminating a program with small chance of success (NoGo); see Chuang-Stein and Kirby (2017). A quantitative decision-making framework addresses the challenge by utilizing available information about safety and efficacy of the drug, target product profile and commercial and regulatory needs. Implementing sound Go/NoGo criteria in early clinical drug development is expected to increase overall performance through better allocation of resources, by limiting the risk of progressing compounds with little efficacy and accelerating development of promising compounds.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we describe how dual criteria for Go/Pause/NoGo decision making are introduced in the case of a single endpoint. In Section 3 we present an example of a clinical study with two endpoints and propose a generalization of a single-endpoint framework to this case. Operating characteristics are discussed in Section 4.

2. Dual criteria for a single endpoint

Lalonde et al. (2007) introduced an approach with two reference values; see also Chuang-Stein and Kirby (2017, Chapter 7.2). Left panel of Figure 1 illustrates a situation targeting a positive response of the treatment of interest (larger is better). A so-called target value (TV) is typically related to commercial viability/target product profile. A so-called Low Reference Value (LRV), sometimes called Minimal Acceptable Value (MAV), may represent a treatment effect of a competitor having mild efficacy. For a discussion on the selection of LRV and TV see Frewer et al. (2016), Section 2.2.

To make a Go decision about progressing a compound into the next stage of development, we would like to ensure that the treatment effect is larger than LRV and to establish a reasonable chance for the

Figure 1: Looking for a positive (left, $LRV < TV$) or negative (right, $LRV > TV$) effect

treatment effect exceeding TV. It is natural to limit chances of (a) progressing the compound when its effect is rather small (“false” Go) or (b) stopping the development when the compound is promising (“false” NoGo). Let $\hat{\mu}$ be an estimate of the “true” treatment effect μ . Two one-sided confidence intervals (CI) for $\hat{\mu}$ are constructed. For a Go decision, the lower bound of the CI must be greater than LRV and the upper bound of the CI must be greater than TV. For a NoGo decision, the upper bound of the CI must be smaller than TV, i.e., chances of a successful trial are low. If a test statistic $\hat{\mu}$ is normally distributed,

$$\hat{\mu} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, V_n^2), \quad (1)$$

where n is trial sample size, then formally,

$$\text{Go decision is made if } \hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n > LRV \text{ and } \hat{\mu} + z_{Up}V_n > TV, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{NoGo decision is made if } \hat{\mu} + z_{Up}V_n < TV, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Pause decision is made if } \hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n < LRV \text{ and } \hat{\mu} + z_{Up}V_n > TV, \quad (4)$$

where z_{Low}, z_{Up} are percentiles for lower and upper boundaries of the CI, respectively. Note that the two one-sided CIs are not necessarily of the same coverage.

To limit chances of a false Go decision, one can select a relatively small α_{falseG} such that the probability of Go decision does not exceed α_{falseG} when $\mu = LRV$. In a similar fashion, a relatively small α_{falseN} can be selected such that the probability of NoGo decision does not exceed α_{falseN} when $\mu = TV$. In a sense, values of α_{falseG} and α_{falseN} are analogous to standard type I and II errors. Notes on how operating characteristics can be derived for normally distributed test statistic $\hat{\mu}$ are provided in the Appendix. It is important to note that operating characteristics (probability of Go, NoGo or Pause decisions) are obtained using assumed true effect values μ . Decision rules are based on estimated (“observed”) values $\hat{\mu}$ of treatment effects and are driven by rules in (2) – (4); see examples in Sections 3, 4 and Frewer et al. (2016, Section 2). For a discussion on “acceptable” operating characteristics, in particular probability of Pause decision, see Frewer et al. (2016), Section 2.4 where the authors use the term “Consider” instead of “Pause” and “Stop” instead of “NoGo”.

When looking for a negative effect, e.g., reduction of blood pressure for hypertensive subjects, it is necessary to change the order of TV and LRV ($TV < LRV$), flip lower and upper bounds of the CI and change the sign of inequalities in (2) – (4); see the right panel of Figure 1. Formally:

$$\text{Go if } \hat{\mu} + z_{up}V_n < LRV \text{ and } \hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n < TV, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{NoGo if } \hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n > TV,$$

$$\text{Pause if } \hat{\mu} + z_{Up}V_n > LRV \text{ and } \hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n < TV.$$

3. Multiple endpoints

In the case of m endpoints of equal importance, with Go/Pause/NoGo individual decisions for each endpoint, there are 3^m different scenarios for making an overall Go, Pause or NoGo decision. With $m = 2$ endpoints, there are 9 different scenarios for an overall decision. In this section we consider the following rules when looking for a positive effect for both endpoints:

- Go when condition (2) is satisfied for both endpoints (both individual Go's).
- NoGo when condition (3) is satisfied for at least one of the endpoints (at least one individual NoGo).
- Pause for the remaining scenarios, i.e., both individual Pause's or a combination of Go and Pause.

Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Go} & \quad \text{if} \quad \hat{\mu}_1 - z_{Low,1}V_{n,1} > LRV_1, \quad \hat{\mu}_1 + z_{Up,1}V_{n,1} > TV_1, & (6) \\ & \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\mu}_2 - z_{Low,2}V_{n,2} > LRV_2, \quad \hat{\mu}_2 + z_{Up,2}V_{n,2} > TV_2; \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{NoGo} \quad \text{if} \quad \hat{\mu}_1 + z_{Up,1}V_{n,1} < TV_1 \quad \text{or} \quad \hat{\mu}_2 + z_{Up,2}V_{n,2} < TV_2; \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Pause} \quad \text{if} \quad \text{all other complementary combinations,}$$

where $\hat{\mu}_i, \mu_i, V_{n,i}, z_{Low,i}, z_{Up,i}, TV_i, LRV_i$ are corresponding values for endpoint $i, i = 1, 2$. See Table 1 where overall decisions are highlighted in bold.

Table 1: Go/Pause/NoGo decisions for two endpoints

	Endpoint 1, NoGo	Endpoint 1, Pause	Endpoint 1, Go
Endpoint 2, Go	NoGo	Pause	Go
Endpoint 2, Pause	NoGo	Pause	Pause
Endpoint 2, NoGo	NoGo	NoGo	NoGo

When looking for a negative effect for both endpoints, use relations (5) to construct decision rules:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Go} & \quad \text{if} \quad \hat{\mu}_1 + z_{Up,1}V_{n,1} < LRV_1, \quad \hat{\mu}_1 - z_{Low,1}V_{n,1} < TV_1, & (8) \\ & \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\mu}_2 + z_{Up,2}V_{n,2} < LRV_2, \quad \hat{\mu}_2 - z_{Low,2}V_{n,2} < TV_2; \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{NoGo} \quad \text{if} \quad \hat{\mu}_1 - z_{Low,1}V_{n,1} > TV_1, \quad \text{or} \quad \hat{\mu}_2 - z_{Low,2}V_{n,2} > TV_2; \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Pause} \quad \text{if} \quad \text{all other complementary combinations.}$$

Figure 2: LRVs and TVs, two endpoints/biomarkers

To illustrate decision rules, we consider a study with two endpoints/biomarkers where each biomarker measures the reduction in the number of “bad” cells after treatment compared to the number of these cells when using the control (larger reduction is better). Figure 2 shows LRVs and TVs in a two-dimensional space. Figure 3 describes various hypothetical scenarios for decisions based on rules (6), (7). Thick green and red lines mark the location of TVs and LRVs, respectively. Top left panel illustrates Go scenarios. Scenario 1, with “1” marking the location of the estimate $(\hat{\mu}_1, \hat{\mu}_2)$, shows the situation where CIs for both endpoints are completely within the Go region: even the left end of CI_i is greater than TV_i , $i = 1, 2$, which mimics the top Go scenario in Figure 1, left panel. In Scenario 4, CIs for both endpoints are analogs of the bottom Go scenario in Figure 1, left panel.

Figure 3: Examples of Go, NoGo, Pause scenarios for two biomarkers, per Table 1

Top right panel of Figure 3 shows examples of NoGo scenarios. Scenarios 1, 2 provide examples of an individual NoGo decision for endpoint 1 (Y -axis) while an individual decision for endpoint 2 would be a Go (X -axis). On the contrary, Scenario 5 shows an example of an individual Go decision for endpoint 1 and NoGo decision for endpoint 2. Bottom panel of Figure 3 illustrates Pause scenarios: individual Pause for both endpoints in Scenario 1, Go for endpoint 1 and Pause for endpoint 2 in Scenario 2, Pause for endpoint 1 and Go for endpoint 2 in Scenario 2.

Note that alternative overall decisions are possible and can be discussed with clinical colleagues. In certain circumstances it may make sense not to stop the development (NoGo) with very good results for one of the endpoints and slightly “missing” Pause decision threshold for another endpoint as in Scenario 1 for NoGo decisions in Figure 3, top right panel. Scenario 2 for Pause decisions may be a candidate for an overall Go decision because of very promising result for endpoint 1 and barely crossing LRV for endpoint 2; see Figure 3, bottom panel. In addition, regions other than of rectangular shapes may be considered for two endpoints.

A similar approach may be used in the case of $m > 2$ endpoints where the enumeration of all possible scenarios will become more laborious and will require extensive discussions with clinical teams.

4. Example: operating characteristics and decision regions

We continue the discussion of the example introduced in Section 3 and look at the reduction in the number of cells after treatment (r_T) compared to the number of cells after administering the control (r_C). The following settings are used:

- $LRV_1 = 25\%$, $TV_1 = 70\%$; $LRV_2 = 10\%$, $TV_2 = 35\%$.
- Risk of (false) Go decision is set at $\alpha_{falseG} = 10\%$ when $\mu_i = LRV_i$, $i = 1, 2$.
- Risk of (false) NoGo decision is set at $\alpha_{falseN} = 10\%$ when $\mu_i = TV_i$, $i = 1, 2$.

In the analysis of cell counts it is standard to use normal approximation for the logarithm of the number of counts and use $\log(r_T/r_C)$ as the target statistic assuming

$$\log\left(\frac{r_T}{r_C}\right) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, V_n^2). \quad (10)$$

Since the goal is in the reduction of cell counts (larger reduction is better), then for logs of the ratio r_T/r_C we are interested in the negative effect and use relations (8), (9) with

$$\widetilde{LRV}_i = \log\left(1 - \frac{LRV_i}{100}\right), \quad \widetilde{TV}_i = \log\left(1 - \frac{TV_i}{100}\right), \quad \text{with } \widetilde{TV}_i < \widetilde{LRV}_i < 0. \quad (11)$$

With equal number of subjects $n_i = n/2$ on each arm and equal variance σ^2 of individual observations, the variance V_n^2 in formula (10) is $V_n^2 = 2\sigma^2/n$. For simulations we use $n_i = 20$ and values of σ_i that resemble historical data: $\sigma_1 = 1.26$, $\sigma_2 = 0.62$.

Figure 4: Operating characteristics: probabilities of Go, Pause, NoGo decisions

Finally, to use the decision rules described in Section 3 for two endpoints, it is necessary to select individual $z_{Low,i}$ and $z_{Up,i}$, $i = 1, 2$. There exist various combinations $(z_{Low,i}, z_{Up,i})$ which guarantee the selected risks α_{falseG} , α_{falseN} . In addition, the correlation $corr$ between endpoints plays a role in the selection of thresholds $\{z\}$. For simulations we restrict ourselves to equal pairs of thresholds: $z_{Low,1} = z_{Low,2}$ and $z_{Up,1} = z_{Up,2}$. When $corr = 0.5$, numerical search leads to values $z_{Low,i} = 0.057$, $z_{Up,i} = 0.22$.

It is worthwhile to remark that while simulations are performed in the space of log-transformed data as in (10), (11), all figures in Sections 3 and 4 are provided in the space of percent reduction (larger is better) because it is much easier to use the latter space for discussions with clinical teams.

In general, to describe probabilities of Go/Pause/NoGo decisions for two endpoints 3-D plots can be generated. To make exposition more transparent, we present 2-D plots: vary values of the true effect for one of the endpoints and show several slices/cross-sections of 3-D plot for a fixed true effect of the second endpoint. In Figure 4 the true effect of biomarker 2 is varied and three slices are shown: for $\mu_1 = LRV_1 = 25\%$ (top left panel), for the intermediate value $\mu_1 = (LRV_1 + TV_1)/2 = 47.5\%$ (top right panel) and for $\mu_1 = TV_1 = 70\%$ (bottom panel). The plots demonstrate the expected trend: as effects increase, probability of Go decision goes up while probability of NoGo decision decreases. When both endpoints are at their LRVs, the probability of Go decision is equal to 10% as prescribed; see green circle at $\mu_2 = 10$, top left panel. Similarly, when both endpoints are at their TVs, the probability of NoGo decision is equal to 10%; see red square at $\mu_2 = 35$, bottom panel. Table 2 shows corresponding probabilities for a number of scenarios.

Table 2: Probabilities of Go/Pause/NoGo decisions for two endpoints, in percent

Scenario	True effect	Pr{Go}	Pr{Pause}	Pr{NoGo}
Low trt effect	$\mu_1 = 25, \mu_2 = 10$	10	7	83
High trt effect	$\mu_1 = 70, \mu_2 = 35$	79	11	10
High/medium trt effect	$\mu_1 = 70, \mu_2 = 22.5$	49	24	27
Medium/low trt effect	$\mu_1 = 47.5, \mu_2 = 10$	18	16	66

Figure 5 presents decision regions on the observed scale. Using relations (8), (9) with \widetilde{LRV}_i , \widetilde{TV}_i introduced in (11) and back-transforming results to the percent-reduction scale, via

$$\mu = 100[1 - \exp(-\widetilde{\mu})],$$

lead to the following regions:

- Go: $R_{Go} = \{\widehat{\mu}_1 > 45, \widehat{\mu}_2 > 23\}$, a region highlighted in light green;
- Pause: $R_{Pause,1} = \{43 \leq \widehat{\mu}_1 \leq 100, 12 \leq \widehat{\mu}_2 \leq 23\}$ and $R_{Pause,2} = \{43 \leq \widehat{\mu}_1 \leq 45, 23 \leq \widehat{\mu}_2 \leq 100\}$, light orange region;
- NoGo: $R_{NoGo} = \{\widehat{\mu}_1 < 43 \text{ or } \widehat{\mu}_2 < 12\}$, light red region.

5. Discussion

Go/NoGo framework is an important facilitator of quantitative decision making in planning and execution of clinical trials. Since the quantitative decision making approach is based on objective criteria which are set up in advance, it is expected to address a critical need to improve productivity of drug development.

In this paper we focused on frequentist methods and efficacy endpoints. It is worthwhile mentioning that Bayesian decision rules could be constructed and implemented; for details, see Chuang-Stein and Kirby (2017), Chapter 7.8 and OKGO tool developed by Cytel (OKGO, 2018). In addition, note

Go/Pause/NoGo, observed scale: n = 20 /arm, Corr = 0.5

Figure 5: 2-D regions for estimates, observed scale

that a similar approach can be developed for safety endpoints or a combination of efficacy and safety endpoints. As underlined earlier, it is important to explore operating characteristics on assumed true effect scale while decision rules have to be clearly communicated on observed (estimated) effect scale.

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Appendix

Using (1) and (2), one gets:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Pr\{Go\} &= Pr\{\hat{\mu} - z_{Low}V_n > LRV, \hat{\mu} + z_{Up}V_n > TV\} = \\
 &= Pr\left\{\frac{\hat{\mu} - \mu}{V_n} > \max\left(z_{Low} + \frac{LRV - \mu}{V_n}, -z_{Up} + \frac{TV - \mu}{V_n}\right)\right\} = \\
 &= 1 - \Phi\left[\max\left(z_{Low} + \frac{LRV - \mu}{V_n}, -z_{Up} + \frac{TV - \mu}{V_n}\right)\right],
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where Φ is a standard normal probability distribution function. It follows from (12) that if $\mu = LRV$, then

$$Pr\{Go\} \leq 1 - \Phi\left(z_{Low} + \frac{LRV - \mu}{V_n}\right) = 1 - \Phi(z_{Low}),$$

and if $z_{low} = \Phi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_{falseG})$, then $P\{Go\} \leq \alpha_{falseG}$. To guarantee the equality in the latter expression, the sum $LRV + z_{Low}V_n$ must be greater than $TV - z_{Up}V_n$.

Similarly,

$$Pr\{NoGo\} = Pr\left\{\frac{\hat{\mu} - \mu}{V_n} < -z_{up} + \frac{TV - \mu}{V_n}\right\} = \Phi\left(-z_{Up} + \frac{TV - \mu}{V_n}\right). \tag{13}$$

It follows from (13) that if $\mu = TV$, then $Pr\{NoGo\} = \Phi(-z_{Up})$, and if $z_{Up} = \Phi^{-1}(1 - \alpha_{falseN})$, then $Pr\{NoGo\} = \alpha_{falseN}$.

The probability of Pause is complementary: $Pr\{Pause\} = 1 - Pr\{Go\} - Pr\{NoGo\}$.

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